

PROPOSALS AND IDEAS ON MOTAPM IN THE GROUP OF GOVERNMENTAL EXPERTS (GGE)

COMMENTS ON THE COORDINATOR'S TEXT

LANDMINE ACTION – FEBRUARY 2006

This paper presents comments on the text of the Coordinator's paper CCW/GGE/XII/WG.2/1/Rev.2

The purpose of the ongoing GGE discussions on MOTAPM must be to strengthen the protection afforded to civilians so that the specific rules relating to MOTAPM are an effective further codification of the relevant general rules relating to means and methods of warfare (such as are contained in Additional Protocol I of 1977 to the Geneva Conventions). Some States Parties have asserted that CCW Amended Protocol II provides sufficient protection for civilians – however, most States Parties consider that some additional protection is needed.

Despite five years of structured discussion, there is currently no agreement on the following issues:

- Severity and nature of the historical or possible future humanitarian impact and cost resulting from MOTAPM use.
- Military utility of different technical configurations of MOTAPM (e.g. are non-detectable mines of significant military value over mines containing 8g of metal?)
- Value of different proposed legal measures to address the humanitarian impact.

In addition, the financial cost of implementing some proposed measures is sometimes cited either directly or indirectly as an impediment to their adoption.

The current disagreement on these key points has unfortunately resulted in a significant proportion of States Parties supporting a text (CCW/GGE/XII/WG.2/1/Rev.2) that does not offer sufficient additional protection to civilians and is not an effective further codification of the relevant general rules. Outside of that bloc some few States Parties assert that the current text is too obstructive to the requirements of military necessity, whilst others assert that it provides too little humanitarian protection.

Victim-activated weapons present a particular risk of striking civilians indiscriminately. Use of MOTAPM should be considered legitimate therefore only *inter alia* if they are directed at specific military objectives and their effects can be limited and proportionate. Doing this requires multiple obligations relating to:

- the exclusion of civilians from the area where MOTAPM are placed.
- timely removal of the threat from MOTAPM when the military objective of their use is no longer valid.

Proposals for ensuring the legitimacy of MOTAPM should be evaluated in terms of these obligations and not seen solely in relation to the existing specific obligations of CCW Amended Protocol II.

COMMENTS ON SPECIFIC SECTIONS

I GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS

Para 2: This paragraph asserts that the objectives of “humanitarian demining” are being addressed through this document. However, the current text legitimates non-detectable mines which are anathema to the humanitarian demining process. The reference to humanitarian demining should be removed so long as non-detectable mines are allowed within the text.

Para 2 (a): Some of the humanitarian problems caused by MOTAPM have resulted from means and methods that would be permissible under this text. Therefore the term “irresponsible” should be removed.

II DEFINITIONS

Para 7 – 8: Without a clear definition of “vehicle” in **Para 7**, and noting **Para 3** of the General Considerations (the exclusion on anti-ship mines), the definition of MOTAPM is not clear. In addition to being unclear, the term MOTAPM does not have any meaning outside of the CCW which may hinder universalisation and communication.

Para 16: The definition of “Perimeter-marked area” as “monitored ..., or protected by fencing” is inadequate, and is weaker than the general requirement to take *all feasible precautions* (**Para 30 (h) ii**). The weakness of this definition is a very serious concern given the importance of the term ‘perimeter-marked area’ in determining different obligations for the recording of MOTAPM use, the detectability of MOTAPM and the active-life of MOTAPM.

As has been noted by the ICRC¹, the current definition “will provide little protection to civilian populations” and it is weaker than the requirement for monitoring *and* protection by fencing that exists for AP mines in Article 5 (2) of Amended Protocol II.

With reference to Amended Protocol II the definition is illogical because in both APII and in this text the purpose is to “ensure the effective exclusion of civilians from the area.” The contents of the area have no bearing on the function being undertaken. The different obligation is therefore not justified by any discussion other than as relates to positive developments in the efficacy of fencing and monitoring practices – and no such developments have been reported to the GGE over the last five years.

On the contrary, Landmine Action’s report *Explosive remnants of war and mines other than anti-personnel mines: Global survey 2003-2004* reported that:

“Very few countries that have MOTAPM contamination as a result of conflict (rather than defensive mining of their own borders) have inherited detailed and comprehensive maps and records of MOTAPM use [This] emphasises that there is little evidence that record-keeping during combat can provide a reliable basis for the protection of civilians. Even where they are kept, records can be lost during fighting as positions are over-run and areas change hands.”

The GICHD in their report on *Humanitarian Impact from MOTAPM* noted:

“Even where minefields have been previously marked, it is common for markings to have been stolen, destroyed during conflict or simply to have deteriorated over time. Where minefields were recorded, these records may only have been partial, they may have been lost, or additional mines may have been subsequently laid in

¹ ICRC, “*Comments on the working paper prepared by the Coordinator on Mines Other than Anti-personnel Mines (MOTAPM) for the 12th Meeting of Governmental Experts to the CCW,*” International Committee of the Red Cross, Geneva.

the area. The lack of information on the location of mines in Angola ... has parallels in most other post-conflict environments.”

And

“Over long periods, minefield fences — if used — will deteriorate, owing to fighting, theft or environmental conditions. All of these factors highlight how record-keeping and marking of minefields cannot be relied upon to stop anti-vehicle mines causing humanitarian problems in the post-conflict environment.

These paragraphs, pointing to the weaknesses of record-keeping, marking and fencing all speak to *the need for multiple mechanisms* in an effort to best protect civilians from MOTAPM. Therefore marking, fencing, monitoring and record-keeping *are all required* in order to work towards “ensur[ing] the effective exclusion of civilians.” Even then, the lack of adequate record-keeping, marking and fencing in many areas of conflict suggests that commitment to these functions is often lacking in real situations.

It is important to note that failures of record-keeping, marking, monitoring and fencing do not need to be wholesale in order to create a widespread fear of MOTAPM contamination which humanitarian demining agencies will need to address.

Additional comments relating to this definition:

Technical Annex B, to be implemented on a voluntary basis, asserts that ‘monitoring or fencing’ represents “best practice”. In fact monitoring or fencing is an obligation in the main body text and is clearly not a “best practice” because it does not represent the best way of “ensuring exclusion of civilians” from an area.

The use of the term “**nuisance minefields**” in **Technical Annex B** is confusing and should be removed. It only appears in this voluntary Annex and is not defined, but it is used in a way that suggests some specific legal status.

III DETECTABILITY OF MOTAPM

The outcomes of a specific phase of active hostilities cannot be predicted with certainty. As a result recording, marking, fencing and monitoring of minefields cannot be relied upon to survive the ravages of conflict. On the other hand it can clearly be expected that some MOTAPM without self-destruction or self-neutralisation mechanisms and self-deactivation features will persist after active hostilities. For this reason it is vitally important that such mines contain *within themselves* characteristics that allow them to be detected and removed in a manner consistent with the legal obligation to limit their effects.

The uncertainty of conflict means that the inherent detectability of MOTAPM should be understood as essential to their legitimacy, regardless of any other controls over their deployment (which cannot be guaranteed to remain effective through active hostilities.)

Para 18 a. The first definition of “detectable” has been imported directly from Technical Annex A (2a) of Amended Protocol II.

However, for the purposes of humanitarian protection “detectable” should mean that the mine can be found using commonly available mine detection equipment within a process that can be expected to occur on sufficient scale and sufficiently quickly to avoid excessive impact on the civilian population.

The current detectability requirement (response signal equivalent to 8g iron in a coherent mass – “8g equivalent”) is insufficient greatly to alleviate problems of MOTAPM contamination. Searching for “8g equivalent” can only proceed at a very slow pace. Given the consistent evidence that marking and record-keeping do not provide a wholly reliable

post-conflict indication of where MOTAPM are located, a very large area must usually be searched in order to remove all of the mines. This pace of clearance, over the area that requires checking, is insufficient to alleviate the humanitarian problems likely to arise from the presence of these mines.

As a result, the humanitarian detectability requirements of MOTAPM and APMs are not the same. Finding a MOTAPM on a 10km stretch of road is not the same challenge as finding an APM in an area of 50 sq m. Indeed, in many circumstances there is no practicable method for fully demining a route of MOTAPM and the best that can be achieved is a form of threat reduction.

Landmine Action reported in its newsletter in 2005² that EU representatives in Sudan have stated “there can be no development in Sudan, especially in the south, without road reconstruction.” As a result:

“Facilitating the reconstruction of over 13,000 kms of high priority routes has become a key priority for UN Mine Action Service (UNMAS) in country. One of the first tasks was the Juba-Yei road. This 160km-long dirt track, pot-holed and near impassable during the wet season, is roughly the same length as the M4, a major UK highway.”

In response to this problem, UNMAS in Sudan have a stated requirement of USD 82 million for 2006. Their primary focus is to *coordinate safe road opening*.

Problems of similarly extensive road contamination have also been evidenced from Angola, Afghanistan and other areas where MOTAPM have created serious humanitarian problems.

Many of the mines that require clearance from these routes were hand emplaced in areas monitored at the time by military personnel. However, during the course of the conflict these checkpoints were over-run and abandoned without the troops having time to remove the MOTAPM emplaced.

The weaknesses of the 8g equivalent detectability requirement have been cited by some States Parties as grounds for abandoning this or any other detectability requirement. Such proposals are at odds with the evidence provided by organisations that undertake the work of post-conflict landmine clearance (see for example UNMAS on *Current and future MOTAPM detection and clearance CCW/GGE/VII/WG.2/WP.4*)

There should be a detectability requirement based on metal content equivalence. The level at which this is set correlates directly to humanitarian protection. The higher the metal content the better the prospects for effective and efficient post-conflict removal. It is not clear that the 8g level has been established through any adequate analysis of the humanitarian benefit it would provide.

The low level of metal content required in **Para 18 (a)** should also be seen in the light of the self-destruction, self-neutralisation and self-deactivation requirements for MOTAPM in the text and the extensive history of manufacturing high-metal content MOTAPM. Given that MOTAPM in perimeter-marked areas are exempt from the detectability requirement (**Para 20**), and given that outside perimeter-marked areas all MOTAPM must have self-destruction or self-neutralisation mechanisms, and self-deactivation features (**Para 24, Para 25**) it is reasonable to ask how the metal content of such mechanisms and features relate to the “8g equivalent” obligation. Whilst it is acknowledged that such devices can be produced with less than 8g equivalent metal content many are likely to contain significantly more metal. This makes it difficult to see why some States Parties can logically oppose this low level of detectability.

Para 18 b. This paragraph is a useful mechanism for addressing the claims made by some States Parties regarding the ready availability of effective alternative detection technologies.

² Campaign, Mine clearance or road construction, Winter 2005

However, it is not clear why a 4/5 vote is acceptable to add new criteria of detectability when the CCW uses consensus for other decisions.

Para 19. This paragraph only serves to render the definition of “detectable” fundamentally unworkable as it is used in subsequent paragraphs (for example **Para 21**). There is no scrutiny process regarding how this form of detectability will “be demonstrated to other States”. Without clarification on this point it is not possible to know whether a particular item is or is not “detectable” according the terms of this text. **Para 19 (b)** is rendered irrelevant by **Para 20**. Given these problems **Para 19** should be deleted.

Para 20 is wholly contrary to the interests of civilian protection and humanitarian demining. Detectability is fundamental to any effort to address the post-conflict impact of MOTAPM and thereby limit the humanitarian effects of their use. Recording, marking, fencing and monitoring of minefields cannot be relied upon to survive the ravages of conflict. As we emphasised regarding **Para 16**, there is a need for multiple mechanisms to enhance the protection of civilians. Even if the definition of perimeter marked area were stronger than that at **Para 16**, this exemption would be unacceptable.

The presence of non-detectable mines means that humanitarian demining must necessarily be undertaken only at the slowest possible pace, *if it is undertaken at all*.

Almost all areas where significant MOTAPM impact has been evidenced have resulted from hand-emplaced mines that were at one time “monitored”. The suggestion that containing non-detectable MOTAPM within perimeter marked areas is sufficient to address the threat that they pose and will pose in the future is not supported by the discussions of the GGE over the last 5 years.

As stated by the USA (CCW/GGE/II/WP.21):

“Undetectable landmines hinder clearing efforts. Without an appropriate metal content, they are difficult to find even in marked and monitored minefields.”

As stated by UNMAS (CCW/GGE/II/WP.14):

“Minimum metal MOTAPM are a serious impediment to efficient clearance operations and increase the possibility of mines being missed by clearance personnel.”

As stated by GICHD (*Humanitarian impact of MOTAPM*):

“Within the range of technical responses available to landmine clearance organisations, metal detection remains the most reliable and readily applicable method for locating anti-vehicle mines accurately. Even where other processes are used to reduce the suspect area, metal detection is often drawn upon to reveal the precise locations of the mines. This process relies on there being sufficient metal content within the mines to make them detectable with the currently available equipment.”

States have not made a substantive case for the military necessity of non-detectable MOTAPM. The practice of states clearly shows that detectable MOTAPM are not without military utility; detectable mines have been produced and used in large numbers. The same States Parties that have argued for non-detectable mines on the grounds of military necessity have also argued that metal detection does not provide an effective tool to address the humanitarian problems of MOTAPM contamination. Elsewhere States Parties have asserted that remotely delivered mines are readily visible - but this is not held to undermine their military utility. These States Parties have also argued that cost is a factor in their opposition to a detectability requirement. However, cost cannot justly be a consideration in determining the legality of the means and methods of war.

Para 21. As has been noted by certain States Parties, the prohibition on production of non-detectable MOTAPM, coupled with clauses that clearly legitimate the use of non-detectable MOTAPM, is contradictory and inconsistent. If the intention of this paragraph is to prohibit non-detectable MOTAPM, which would be very welcome, then this should be done in a direct and logically coherent way. Also the definition of 'detectable' is open to question as a result of **Paras 18 and 19**.

IV ACTIVE LIFE OF MOTAPM

There is no justification for an exclusion of hand-emplaced MOTAPM from the obligation for other MOTAPM outside perimeter-marked areas to have mechanisms and features to limit their life. Without such obligations there is no adequate mechanism for limiting the effects of such mines. Almost all areas that have suffered severe humanitarian impact from MOTAPM suffered primarily from the effects of hand-emplaced persistent mines. Without addressing this requirement the text does virtually nothing to address the primary cause of humanitarian suffering from MOTAPM.

Para 24. In the light of **Para 26** referring to the voluntary **Technical Annex B/2** for the specifications of SD/SDA or SN/SDA and for the mechanisms for evaluating the reliability of such systems, the prohibition in **Para 24** and **Para 25** is very weak. It is not clear in **Para 24** how or where the "military purpose for which it was emplaced" will be recorded. In the absence of any fixed time-frame this becomes the binding point of reference for the prohibition - but it is not detailed or explained in any way.

The voluntary requirements of Technical Annex B/2 must be made mandatory within the body text and coupled with some transparent and independent mechanism for the demonstration and monitoring of SD/SDA or SN/SDA reliability.

VI FUZE DESIGN AND SENSORS OF MOTAPM

Para 29. For States Parties to the Convention on The Prohibition of Anti-Personnel Mines the voluntary framework presented here is over-ridden by the definitions of that Convention which prohibits anti-vehicle mines configured in such a way as to be initiated by an unintentional act of a person.

VII. USE, RECORDING AND REMOVAL OF MOTAPMS, AND MINEFIELDS AND MINED AREAS OF MOTAPMS.

Para 30 (f) i. "Road" should be added to the list of objects normally dedicated to civilian purposes.

Para 30 (h) ii. The obligation to take "all feasible precautions" is stronger than the definition of perimeter marked area at **Para 16**.

Para 32. There should be some definition of which areas in what circumstances can be considered "active hostilities". It has become common practice for some states to assert that they are "in a time of war" without making any declaration of war and without any clarity regarding the geographic boundaries of the conflict. Such assertions have been held to affect their obligations under international humanitarian law. A definition of "active hostilities" would help to ensure that **Para 32 (a)** is not undermined by an overly broad interpretation of **Para 32 (b)**.

Para 33 (a) As above, a definition of "active hostilities" would strengthen this paragraph.

VIII TRANSFERS

Para 35 (b) This may be rendered unworkable due to the lack of a clear definition regarding detectable at **Paras 18 & 19**.

Para 35 (f) For States Parties to the Convention on The Prohibition of Anti-Personnel Mines such a transfer may be illegal.

Richard Moyes

Policy & Research Manager, Landmine Action

rmoyes@landmineaction.org

+44 (0)7875 509 120